

Catalytic Formation of Methane from Carbon Monoxide and Hydrogen.

Part II.

Production of Fuel Gases rich in Methane

BY

KHITINDRA MOHAN CHAKRAVARTY

AND

JNANENDRA CHANDRA GHOSH

Blue water gas and carburetted water gas have the following approximate composition :—

	H ₂	CO	CO ₂	CH ₄	N ₂	Unsaturated hydrocarbon.
Blue water gas	49	42	4	5	4.5	—
Carburetted water gas	38	27	3	17	5	10

Owing to the poisonous properties of blue water gas with its high carbon monoxide content it is not used for distribution in a city supply; "the chief application of blue water gas is in connection with the manufacture of carburetted water gas," which "is even used for distribution without admixture in the United States." (Greenwood, *Industrial Gases*, pp. 324-325.)

It has been noted in the previous paper that sugar-charcoal-nickel catalyst remains active for months in a gas mixture H₂ : CO :: 3 : 1 and always produced a certain amount of CO₂ and CH₄ according to the reaction,

This led to the hope that this catalyst might be used for converting blue water gas into carburetted water gas. Armstrong and Hilditch observed (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1923, [A], 103, 27) that when a mixture of carbon monoxide

and hydrogen was passed over nickel catalyst, the above was the only reaction taking place 'towards 300°C.' Unfortunately Armstrong and Hilditch have not described their method of preparing this catalyst and only mention that nickel was deposited on kieselguhr. They advance the view that the reaction takes place in two stages :

The nickel of the catalyst studied in this paper was deposited on pumice stone, sometimes along with sugar charcoal and the effects of various promoters on these catalysts have also been investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Nickel Catalyst with Sugar Charcoal and Pumice powder as supporting Material with or without Promoter.—A solution of weighed quantities of sugar, nickel acetate and promoter, if any, was prepared and concentrated carefully so as to give on addition of pumice powder a semi-solid mass. Merck's ignited pumice stone was broken to small pieces, kept for three days in nitric acid, washed and ignited before use. This product was mixed with a small quantity of powdered ammonium carbonate and heated in a smooth nickel crucible with the lid on to dull redness. When the product swelled up the lid was opened and stronger heating applied till the carbon in the catalyst began to burn by itself. With very fine pumice powder the catalyst was neither very voluminous nor very active. Other experimental details were the same as in the previous paper excepting that the reacting gas mixture had the composition $\text{H}_2 : \text{CO} :: 1 : 1$.

Table I gives a comparative idea of the efficiency of the catalyst for 1 : 3 and 1 : 1 mixture of CO and H₂,

TABLE I.

<i>Catalyst</i>	Pumice	:	Nickel acetate	:	Sugar,
	17		4.7		15.
Quantity of nickel per c.c. of catalyst	...		...		0.018 gm.
Temperature of reduction	...		...		265°

S.V.—c.c. of gas per c.c. of catalyst space per minute.

H ₂ : CO	Temp.	S. V.	% OH ₄	% CO ₂	% CO	% H ₂
3 : 1	90°	1.22	50	12.5	0	37.7
	„	1.63	40.2	10.3	2.3	46.8
	356°	1.52	54.2	10.8	0	85.1
1 : 1	310°	0.38	18.5	9.6	43.6	23.1
	355°	0.59	28.4	19.9	29.1	24.5*
	385°	0.34	36.0	34.0	11.9	18*

From Table I it is clear that the efficiency of the catalyst for reaction (2) is small and an attempt was made to improve the efficiency by various promoters. Ceria as promoter, found by Medsforth (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 1452) to be most efficient for the reaction,

is without much influence on pumice-nickel-sugar catalyst in promoting reaction (2) as will be evident from Table II.

TABLE II.

<i>Catalyst</i>	Pumice	:	Nickel acetate	:	Sugar	:	Cerium Nitrate.
	17		3.5		11.3		0.258
Quantity of nickel per c.c. of catalyst	...		...		...		0.0155 gm.
Temp. of reduction	...		...		...		265°

Temp.	S. V.	% OH ₄	% CO ₂	% CO	% H ₂
350°	.4	28.7	21.3	27.3	22.4*
350°	2.6	10	4.7	48	37.2.

* See footnote, p. 161.

Vanadic acid was found by Medsforth to be the least efficient promoter for reaction (3). It was considered interesting to investigate its efficiency for reaction (2).

TABLE III.

Catalyst		Pumice	:	Nickel acetate		
		3		1		
Quantity of nickel per c.c. catalyst				...	0.037 gm.	
Temp. of reduction				...	280°	
Temp.	S.V.	% CH ₄	% CO ₂	% CO	% H ₂	
308°	.63	37	31.9	12.6	18.5*	
Catalyst		Pumice	:	Nickel acetate	:	Vanadic acid
		17		3.5		0.3
Nickel per c.c. of catalyst						0.225 gm
Temp. reduction...						286°
Temp.	S. V.	% CH ₄	% CO ₂	% CO	% H ₂	
(1) 304°	.68	51.9	43.2	3	18*	
Followed by a rapid fall in activity.						
A day after (1).						
(2) 302°		0.42	29	22	31	18
Five days after (2).						
(3) 305°		0.44	21	9	47	23
After two days' working at temperature between 460° and 524°.						
(4) 304°		0.49	14	4.8	50	31

It will be seen from Table III that vanadic acid is a very efficient promoter on nickel catalyst for reaction (2). But unfortunately the activity does not remain constant as will be evident from the data given. After 9 days' work the CO₂ formation at 304° drops from 43% to 5%.†

It was observed that a considerable deposit of nickel formed on the sides of the tube and a deposit of carbon on the pumice stone. Deposition of nickel was also observed when the catalyst was worked even below 305°. The fall of activity was also noticed when the catalyst

* The excess of hydrogen in the initial readings is mainly due to hydrogen already present in the reaction tube.

† After each day's experiment the catalyst was allowed to cool in an atmosphere of H₂ and CO mixture (1: 1) for about 18 hours. The catalyst was worked almost continuously for 6 hours every day.

was cooled in an atmosphere of pure H_2 during intervals between successive days' work. But here the deposition of nickel could not be observed.

It will be noticed from the analytical data at 300° to 305° that with continued use, the difference between the percentage yields of CH_4 and CO_2 increases continuously. This is ascribed to the fact that reaction (3) is taking place in larger portion.

An attempt, was made to find out if by the use of sugar charcoal the high efficiency observed in the catalyst, pumice-nickel-vanadic-acid, can be maintained steady. The results are summarised in Table IV.

TABLE IV.

<i>Catalyst</i>	Pumice powder :	Nickel acetate :	Vanadic Acid :	Sugar.
	17	3.5	0.25	10
	Quantity of nickel per c. c. of catalyst . . . 0.0157 gm.			
	Temp. of reduction 279°			

Temp.	S. V.	OH_4	CO_2	CO	H_2	Diff.
300° ...	54	19.2	11.1	42.7	27	0.5
351° ...	1.96	26	25.4	25.3	23.2	-0.9
" ...	2.7	24.5	20.4	32	23.4	-0.6
353° ...	4.7	14	6	48	32	0
406° [A] ...	5.7	34.2	23.5	14.6	17	3.8*
406° [B] ...	10.8	25.3	24	26.2	24	2.6*
451° [C] ...	25.4	20	16	36	27.6	-0.4
506° ...	36.9	18.1	14.2	37.2	30.8	1 *
540° ...	41.9	19.4	17.4	32.5	30.5	2 *
600° ...	45.5	8.5	5.5	46.3	39.6	-0.6

* It was invariably found that as the temp. of the catalyst was raised the analysis of the outflow gases for the first few minutes showed an excess of hydrogen. This was due to the fact that a large amount of hydrogen was absorbed by nickel-charcoal surface part of which was given out when the temperature was made higher.

A large number of experiments were carried out with this catalyst for months and the data recorded in Table IV are only typical. The significant fact to be noted in connection with this catalyst is that its activity is rather low at low temperature; but as temp. rises the activity rapidly increases. The activity remains steady for months if the reaction temp. is not maintained above 500°. Continued reaction at 500° for some time completely spoils the catalyst. When not in use the catalyst was kept in an atmosphere of hydrogen. It was noticed generally that with increase in *S. V.* at constant temperature the difference between the percentage yield of methane and carbon dioxide increased indicating that high *S. V.* favours reaction (3). The same phenomenon was observed in Table IV, where temperature and *S. V.* were kept practically constant but activity of the catalyst was diminishing. Both the reactions (2) and (3) take place with evolution of heat and it was found that at about 400° the reaction proceeded quickly enough to maintain constant the temperature of the catalyst-space without extraneous heating.

Pumice and sugar charcoal were in some experiments replaced by coconut charcoal. The initial activity was found to be quite high at low temperature but unfortunately the activity did not remain steady. It also did not increase much with increase of reaction temperature. Besides vanadium pentoxide, ferric oxide was found to be a suitable promoter. Table V gives the experimental data.

TABLE V.

<i>Catalyst</i>	Pumice :	Nickel acetate :	Ferric nitrate :	Sugar	
	17	3.5	0.8	17	
Nickel per c.c. of catalyst		...	...	0.01 gm.	
Temp. of reduction		...	...	260°	
Temp.	<i>S. V.</i>	OH ₂	CO ₂	CO	H ₂
305°	78	19.6	8	48.8	23.8

It will be noticed that with this catalyst the difference between the percentage of CH_4 and CO_2 is very large, more than 50% of CH_4 yield being due to reaction (3).

Table VI gives the approximate calorific value per 22.4 litres.

TABLE VI.

	CH_4	CO_2	CO	H_2	N_2	Unsaturated hydrocarbon	Calorific value
Carburetted water gas	17	3	27	38	5	10	100,000
Methane-rich gas							
<i>vide</i> Table IV [A]	34.2	33.5	14.6	17	...	...	94,000
" [B]	25.3	24	26.2	24	...	...	87,000
" [C]	20	16	36	27.6	...	...	85,000

At 406° the space velocity with catalyst (pumice-nickel-vanadium-oxide-sugar-charcoal) in Table IV is quite large and the resulting gases have composition comparable to that of carburetted water gas, the calorific value of the resulting gas mixture being somewhat less than carburetted water gas. This is due to the fact that the large amount of CO_2 present in the mixture acts merely as a diluent and if this could be removed by scrubbing, a gas of very high calorific value could be obtained.

The reactions taking place at the catalyst surface can be found out by a consideration of the composition of the incoming and effluent gases. It is clear that if reaction (2) were alone taking place, the percentage of carbon dioxide and methane would have been the same in the outflow gases. As a matter of fact the yield of methane is always greater than that of carbon dioxide. It thus appears that a part of the methane may have been produced by reaction (3). If these were the only two reactions taking place and if w , x , y and z be the respective volumes of CH_4 , CO_2 , CO and

H₂ in the outflow gases in a certain interval, then the incoming gases in that interval would consist of $(w+x+y)$ vol. of CO and the same volume of hydrogen. The volume of hydrogen used up therefore is $(w+x+y)-z$.

The quantity of hydrogen consumed in reaction (2) is $2x$ and that in reaction (3) is $3(w-x)$. Therefore $3(w-x)+2x$ should be equal to $(w+x+y)-z$. In many cases this equation holds good, indicating that an amount of methane equivalent to CO₂ is produced according to reaction (2) and the excess of methane by reaction (3). The last vertical column in Table IV gives the difference between the values of $(w+x+y)-z$ and $3(w-x)+2x$ for each of the experimental observations. It is evident from the table that this difference is generally very small.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,

DACCA UNIVERSITY.

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